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Supercharging the Benefits of Low Carbon Fuel Standards

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Summary

Market-based mechanisms to decarbonize transportation fuels can provide significant value to entities in the electric vehicle (EV) charging ecosystem. However, this value is not always captured by key stakeholders – undermining the effectiveness of market-based regulations and further challenging the economics of transportation electrification. This paper identifies how public entities could navigate structural challenges and opportunities associated with market-based decarbonization policies to drive EV adoption. We provide a menu of potential options these entities could pursue to support transportation electrification through the lens of California’s Low Carbon Fuel Standard and the San Diego Association of Government’s upcoming EV charger incentive program.

Keywords: charger, incentive, market, policy, low carbon fuel standard

1 Introduction

Electric vehicles (EVs) are widely recognized for their low “well-to-wheels” emissions relative to internal combustion engine vehicles [1]. Due to the superior efficiency of electric motors and the continued decarbonization of the electricity system, EVs are well-positioned to become an increasingly important solution to reduce transportation sector greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in a carbon-constrained economy. Despite the growth of charging station incentive programs in some areas, access to charging infrastructure continues to hinder EV adoption.

Policymakers interested in developing markets for low carbon fuels have explored, and in several cases implemented, low carbon fuel standards (LCFS). LCFS refers to market-based regulations that reduce the overall carbon intensity (CI) of transportation fuels sold in a jurisdiction. California, Oregon, and British Columbia currently administer LCFS while the Puget Sound region of Washington, Colorado, and Canada are considering the implementation of LCFS. Although LCFS are fuel-neutral in nature, electricity specifically used to fuel EVs has the potential to generate credits that can be sold to parties regulated by the LCFS (e.g., refiners that produce gasoline and diesel) and offset the costs associated with EV charging. However, structural dynamics of LCFS pose challenges for EV charging station owners and operators seeking to sell their credits in LCFS markets and maximize their credit generation opportunities. These conditions can diminish the

effectiveness of LCFS policy and limit the financial incentives available to support transportation electrification.

At the same time, many government entities have developed and implemented programs to incentivize the deployment of EV charging stations in jurisdictions with LCFS policy. These programs have significant potential to integrate LCFS provisions into their design; if done strategically, these programs can support LCFS goals while simultaneously supporting EV adoption and sustainable EV charging economics. Revenues generated from the LCFS could be disbursed to charging station site hosts or used towards the funding of additional EV charging station incentives. We assess these opportunities through the lens of California’s Low Carbon Fuel Standard (CA-LCFS) and the San Diego Association of Government’s (SANDAG) EV charger incentive program partnership with the California Energy Commission (CEC) [2][3]. These opportunities are not exclusive to California: they apply broadly to other governments and government entities considering LCFS policy implementation.

2 LCFS Background

2.1 LCFS Overview

LCFS is a market-based regulation that aims to reduce the average CI of transportation fuels sold in a jurisdiction. CI refers to the measurement of GHG emissions associated with the production, distribution, and consumption of transportation fuels and is typically measured in grams of carbon dioxide equivalent per megajoule of fuel (gCO_{2e}/MJ). LCFS sets an annual CI target that declines until a CI reduction goal is achieved. To encourage the uptake of low carbon fuels, CI targets are set below the CI of petroleum fuels such as gasoline and diesel [4][5]. Once an annual CI target is set, regulated fuel suppliers – typically refiners producing gasoline and diesel – are required to achieve compliance by reducing the CI of their fuels. Fuels that have a CI above the target will generate deficits proportional to the amount of fuel sold, while fuels that have a carbon intensity below the target will generate credits expressed in tons of CO_{2e} avoided relative to the CI target. Fuel suppliers have two primary pathways to achieve compliance: they can reduce the CI of their fuels by switching to or incorporating lower carbon fuels, or they can purchase credits in a credit market. The figure below illustrates the relationship between annual CI targets, fuel CIs, and credit balances.

Figure 1: Illustrative Graphic of California LCFS Compliance Curve (Source: CARB)

As credit values rise, regulated fuel suppliers are encouraged to produce lower-carbon fuels to reduce the price risk associated with purchasing credits in the marketplace. LCFS fundamentally encourages economic CO₂e reductions by pushing regulated fuel suppliers to evaluate whether CI reductions can be achieved more cost-effectively through strategic internal investments and decisions or by purchasing credits on the market to offset their deficits.

The CA-LCFS is administered by the California Air Resources Board (CARB). CA-LCFS is the most significant GHG emissions reduction program addressing transportation sector emissions in the state and is a critical strategy for achieving the state’s broader climate goals. Since program implementation began in 2010 through 2018, the LCFS has mitigated over 38 million tons of CO₂e emissions, increased alternative fuels use by 74 percent, and reduced petroleum use by 51.86 billion liters [6]. After the CA-LCFS was amended and extended in 2018, the standard now requires a 7.5 percent CI reduction of all regulated transportation fuels by 2020 and a 20 percent reduction by 2030 from 2010 levels [7].

2.2 Electric Fuel and LCFS

Electricity as a transportation fuel has played a relatively minor role in CA-LCFS compliance compared to other alternative fuels such as ethanol and renewable diesel. However, electricity’s contributions to the CA-LCFS are continuing to grow as transportation electrification advances in California. Fig. 2 illustrates the alternative fuel volumes and credits generated between 2011 and 2018.

Figure 2: LCFS Fuel and Credit Volumes (Source: CARB)

LCFS CI targets are set at a level that enable lower carbon transportation fuels – including electricity – generate credits that can be sold into the credit market. This credit generation opportunity can yield revenues for entities that purchase, install, or operate EV charging infrastructure – improving the economics of charging station operations necessary to accelerate transportation electrification. Based on the CA-LCFS credit generation formula, a Level 2 (L2) charging station that dispenses 4,000 kilowatt-hours (kWh) of electricity annually to light-duty EVs would generate approximately 3-4 LCFS credits in 2020 [8]. In January 2020, the average price of credits transferred in the CA-LCFS was \$200 per credit [9]. Credit prices have increased over the years as the program’s CI targets become more stringent.

3 EV Charger Incentive Program Background

3.1 EV Charging Station Costs and Incentive Program Overview

To reduce GHG emissions and improve air quality, many local, regional, and state government agencies have established EV charger incentive programs. These programs seek to mitigate the cost associated with purchasing, installing, and operating EV charging stations [10]. The cost of EV charging equipment is a non-trivial expense for site hosts and EV charging service providers that seek to own EV charging infrastructure [11]. The table below presents the estimated costs associated with various EV charging technologies in the United States.

Table 1 Public Charging Station Hardware Costs (Source: International Council on Clean Transportation)

Charger Type	Network Type	Per-Plug Cost	Total Cost
Level 1 single charger	Non-networked	\$813	\$813
Level 2 single charger	Networked	\$3,127	\$3,127
Level 2 dual-plug charger	Networked	\$2,793	\$5,586
Direct Current Fast Charger (DCFC) 50 kW	Networked	\$28,401	\$28,401
Direct Current Fast Charger (DCFC) 150 kW	Networked	\$75,000	\$75,000

These costs do not include the “make-ready” costs associated with additional electrical infrastructure needed to support charging station deployments, installation costs, permitting fees, taxes, or networking fees for networked charging equipment [12]. Although charging stations have been deployed at workplaces, residences, and other commercial properties as an amenity, a direct-revenue business model for EV charging services is challenging for site hosts looking to make a return on investment or “break even” over a reasonable timeframe – underscoring the near-term importance of EV charging station incentive programs while the EV market develops [13].

3.2 California Electric Vehicle Infrastructure Project

One of the most well-funded charging station incentive programs in the United States is the California Electric Vehicle Infrastructure Project (CALeVIP) – funded by the CEC and administered by the Center for Sustainable Energy (CSE). CALeVIP seeks to help address the state’s charging infrastructure gap for L2 and DCFC stations by developing regional incentive programs that accelerate charging station deployment and EV adoption. In August 2019, the CEC announced it would establish a CALeVIP program in San Diego County in partnership with SANDAG and the San Diego County Air Pollution Control District (APCD). The CEC is funding program administration and DCFC incentives while SANDAG and APCD are co-funding administration and L2 station incentives. SANDAG anticipates allocating at least \$1.5 million per year toward L2 station rebates for the first three years of the program and \$30 million for public charging infrastructure between 2020-2050 [14]. The CEC has also expressed an interest in incorporating LCFS provisions into the final CALeVIP program design [15].

4 Structural Challenges Associated with LCFS Credit Integration into EV Charger Incentive Programs

4.1 Market Liquidity Issues

There is significant value from LCFS programs that is currently left untapped by EV charging station owners and site hosts. However, individual charging station owners face a significant hurdle that limits their ability to monetize credits in CA-LCFS: the lack of liquidity in the CA-LCFS credit trading market [16]. In California, regulated fuel suppliers typically seek to purchase large volumes of credits – often time exceeding 1,000 credits per transaction. High credit transaction thresholds do not pose a significant barrier to credit monetization for EV charging service providers and fleet owners that own charging equipment and generate large volumes of credits across a network of charging stations [17]. However, for site hosts that own limited quantities of EV charging stations, it is challenging to generate enough credits to execute transactions on the CA-LCFS market; many publicly available L2 stations are not owned by EV charging service providers but instead sold to site hosts to own and operate. Although the site host is generating credits from EV charging, the value of those credits does not materialize unless they can be claimed and sold.

Credit aggregation could resolve challenges associated with the CA-LCFS credit market. For residential EV charging, California’s investor owned utilities have been responsible for reporting, aggregating, monetizing, and disbursing credit value back to their customers in the form of EV rebates and incentives per the CA-LCFS regulation [18]. There is no comparable aggregator designated for non-residential EV charging. Unmonetized LCFS credits not only represent a lost opportunity for site hosts: they can also increase LCFS compliance costs in periods when the credit market tightens.

4.2 Zero Carbon Intensity Electricity Credit Aggregation Challenges

The CA-LCFS also creates challenges for site hosts seeking to lower the CI of their electricity using zero-carbon renewable electricity generation. Power sector emissions are dynamic and depend on the mix of resources available on the grid at any given time. To simplify credit generation calculations, LCFS policies may assume an average CI for the grid and may not accurately account for the CI of the electricity used to fuel an EV. If properly accounted for, EVs charged with renewable electricity can generate substantially more credits per unit of fuel than “grid-average” electricity [19]. In the CA-LCFS, credit-generating parties have the option to reduce the CI of dispensed electricity by purchasing and retiring renewable energy credits (RECs) generated from zero-carbon resources [20]. RECs that are used for LCFS compliance cannot be used for compliance with California’s Renewable Portfolio Standard (RPS), which requires increasingly greater percentages of California’s electricity demand to be served by renewable electricity generation resources [21].

Just as EV charging station owners face challenges to execute transactions on the CA-LCFS credit market, these entities may also encounter difficulties purchasing limited quantities of RECs needed to take advantage of the CA-LCFS’s zero-carbon intensity provisions for EV charging. Similar to CA-LCFS credits, RECs are typically bought and sold in quantities much larger than what a typical site host would need to cover their electricity generation. Even if site hosts have on-site renewable electricity generation that they can claim RECs from, they likely will not have sufficient CA-LCFS credits that can be sold in the CA-LCFS market without aggregation.

4.3 LCFS Education and Awareness Gaps

LCFS policies are not widely known among the general public and prospective EV charging station site hosts. As a result, many site hosts are unaware that they could potentially benefit from opting in to LCFS policies.

ICF analysis of CARB data suggests that approximately 12,000 L2 charging stations in California are not currently participating in the CA-LCFS, even though they are eligible to generate credits [22]. This statistic reflects the challenge of effectively communicating and educating non-expert site hosts on the benefits of LCFS policies.

Additionally, there are few examples of EV charging station incentive programs that include provisions on LCFS. CALeVIP's Sacramento County Incentive Project stipulates that all credits generated from incentivized L2 chargers will be assigned to the Sacramento Municipal Utility District (SMUD) [23]. The credits could then be monetized by SMUD to create additional funds for EV charger incentives in the program. Anaheim Public Utilities' (APU's) Public Access Electric Vehicle Charging Station Rebate Program requires participating site hosts to relinquish any future CA-LCFS credits generated to APU in the program agreement form [24]. APU notes that CA-LCFS credit sales revenue is a primary source of funding for the program [25]. In most cases, however, incentive programs do not establish guidance or requirements for the use of CA-LCFS credits. Without clear information or support from program administrators, site hosts will likely remain unaware of the CA-LCFS and their ability to generate credits from EV charging. Even when site hosts are made aware of the program, it is unclear if they will have the opportunity to take advantage of the CA-LCFS given the aforementioned market barriers to entry.

5 Public Agencies as Facilitators of LCFS Policy

Given these structural barriers in the CA-LCFS and the risks they pose to achieving the policy's goals, there exists a clear motivation to improve site hosts' ability to participate in the CA-LCFS. Public agencies have the potential to link LCFS programs to EV charging station incentive programs in a manner that provides new revenue for incentive programs, improves station economics for site hosts, increases the use of renewable electricity as the fuel for EVs, and addresses information asymmetry in the CA-LCFS. These issues are discussed within the context of the CALeVIP program for the San Diego region.

5.1 Public Agencies as LCFS Credit Aggregators

Public agencies have several options for enabling site host participation in LCFS through their EV charging station incentive programs. First, public agencies can act as aggregators of LCFS credits. By pooling together credits generated from site hosts, agencies could effectively execute LCFS transactions as a regulated party and unlock value that may otherwise have not materialized but for credit aggregation. Public agencies may use the credit value to fund additional incentives for charging stations or cover program administration costs. These public agencies may also return the value of the credits to site hosts to help offset costs associated with the operation and maintenance of the charging equipment that they own [26]. A hybrid approach could allocate funding among these objectives.

Public agencies could also contract with third party aggregators to generate value from the LCFS. These aggregators would be responsible for performing all aggregation, transaction, and reporting requirements to comply with LCFS regulation. This arrangement may require public agencies to release competitive bids for LCFS aggregation services and increase short-term administrative burden. However, contracting with third party aggregators may reflect a more efficient allocation of resources to integrate and derive value from LCFS in EV charging station incentive programs.

ICF assessed the potential CA-LCFS credit revenue generation from the estimated quantity of L2 stations deployed between 2020-2030 as a result of SANDAG's partnership funding dedicated to CALeVIP using the assumptions and formulas outlined in Table 2 [27].

Table 2 CA-LCFS Credit Generation Assumptions and Outputs for CALeVIP (San Diego Region)

Assumption	Assumption Abbreviation	Assumption Value
Annual L2 Ports Deployed	PD	279 ports
Average Annual Per Port Utilization	U	2,000 kWh 4,000 kWh 6,000 kWh
Energy Density of Electricity	ED	3.6 megajoules/kWh
Energy Economy Ratio	EER	3.4
Carbon Intensity of Electricity	CI _{Electricity}	Adopted from LCFS regulation
Annual Carbon Intensity of Gasoline Target	CI _{Gasoline}	Adopted from LCFS regulation
Average LCFS Credit Price	P _{LCFS}	\$150/ton \$175/ton \$200/ton
Brokerage Fee	B _{LCFS}	\$0.25/credit
Minimum Credit Transaction Threshold	MC	1,000 credits
Discount Rate	DR	5%
Program Year	t	1-10

Output	Output Abbreviation	Formula
Annual Per Port Credit Generation	CG	$(CI_{gasoline}^t - CI_{Electricity}^t / EER) * ED * EER * U * 10^{-6}$
Annual LCFS Credit Revenue	CR	$(CG * (P_{LCFS} - B_{LCFS}) / (1 + DR)^t)$
Maximum LCFS Credit Transactions Executed	TE	CG / MC

In a scenario where average annual per port utilization equals 4,000 kWh and the average LCFS credit price is \$175 per ton, the program could yield 57,814 LCFS credits and the estimated cumulative program-wide revenue received from selling these credits equals \$7,390,000. The graph below (Fig. 3) illustrates the estimated cumulative program-wide revenue generated from LCFS credits under the various port utilization and LCFS credit price scenarios.

Figure 3 Estimated Cumulative LCFS Credit Revenue from CALeVIP L2 Stations 2020-2030 (San Diego Region)

In all scenarios, SANDAG could generate significant revenue from LCFS credit sales that could be recycled into the program or disbursed to help participating site hosts offset station operation and maintenance costs. Credit revenue is heavily dependent on station utilization, and CALeVIP can help encourage higher utilization rates by ensuring charging stations are shared-use, easily accessible for all EV drivers, and marked with the appropriate signage.

5.2 Public Agencies as REC Purchasers

ICF analysis of CA-LCFS credit generation opportunities in CALeVIP explored the potential for leveraging the CA-LCFS's zero-CI electricity provisions to pair RECs with electricity as a fuel for EV charging. Additional assumptions and outputs for the low-CI electricity analysis are outlined in Table 3.

Table 3 CA-LCFS Credit Generation Assumptions and Outputs for CALeVIP with RECs (San Diego Region)

Assumption	Assumption Abbreviation	Assumption Value
Carbon Intensity of Electricity	$CI_{\text{Electricity}}$	0
REC Price	P_{REC}	\$20/REC
Brokerage Fee per REC Transaction	B_{REC}	2.5%/transaction
Output	Output Abbreviation	Formula
Annual REC Demand	D_{REC}	$PD * U / 1000$
Annual REC Cost	C_{REC}	$D_{\text{REC}} * P_{\text{REC}} / (1 + DR)^t * (1 + B_{\text{REC}})$
Annual Low-CI LCFS Credit Revenue	C_{RL}	$CR - C_{\text{REC}}$

In a scenario where average annual per port utilization equals 4,000 kWh and the average LCFS credit price is \$175 per ton, the program could yield 75,457 LCFS credits and the estimated cumulative program-wide revenue received from selling these credits equals \$8,561,000 – a 16 percent increase in LCFS credit revenue over the baseline scenario without RECs. The graph below (Fig. 4) illustrates the estimated incremental cumulative program-wide revenue generated from LCFS credits with zero-CI electricity under the various port utilization and LCFS credit price scenarios. In all scenarios, incremental revenue is generated compared to the baseline scenario.

Figure 4 Estimated Cumulative LCFS Credit Revenue from CALeVIP L2 Stations with RECs 2020-2030 (San Diego Region)

While the incorporation of RECs augments LCFS credit generation opportunities for public agencies, there are several challenges associated with pairing RECs and electricity used to fuel EVs in California. First, purchasing RECs generally requires a broker – raising transaction costs for executing trades. Additionally, the Western Renewable Energy Generation Information System (WREGIS), the entity responsible for issuing and tracking RECs across much of the western United States, does not get involved in REC pricing or report prices of RECs traded [28]. In contrast, CARB reports CA-LCFS credit trading activity and pricing on a weekly and monthly basis – providing market participants with greater credit price transparency. Finally, the incremental benefits of using renewable electricity compared to “grid-average” electricity will shrink over time for two related reasons. As the CA-LCFS annual CI targets decrease, each unit of carbon-free electricity generates fewer credits. The increasing stringency of California’s RPS may also decrease the available supply of RECs available for use in the CA-LCFS and raise credit prices. In a scenario where CA-LCFS credit prices are \$175, a REC price of \$42 or above will likely erode any of the monetary benefit of pursuing zero-CI electricity for the purpose participating in the CA-LCFS. In sum, there are near-term opportunities to incentivize EV charging paired with RECs, but the complexity of procuring RECs and the long-term market uncertainty creates a challenging environment for stakeholders to unlock this value.

5.3 Public Agencies as LCFS Awareness Builders

Public agencies have a role to play in increasing awareness around LCFS in their EV charging station incentive programs. Greater understanding of LCFS policies and credit monetization among risk-averse site hosts may encourage greater participation in incentive programs. Public agencies can foster this understanding by including LCFS information on program websites, incentive application forms, and in program marketing material. At a minimum, this LCFS information should include: program objectives and targets, eligible fuels, and credit generation mechanics. Public agencies should also include information as to how LCFS credit revenue generated by their incentive programs will be spent and how that revenue will produce environmental benefits as well as benefits for participating site hosts. Public agencies may also want to provide fleet managers with more information on how large fleets can directly participate in LCFS markets to offset vehicle fuel and charging station operations and maintenance costs. SANDAG is well-positioned to incorporate greater

CA-LCFS awareness-building efforts into the rollout of the forthcoming CALeVIP program in the San Diego region and future EV charging incentive programs once CALeVIP funding is expended.

6 Looking Forward

Widespread transportation electrification remains critical for reducing GHG emissions in a manner consistent with governments' climate and air quality goals. LCFS regulations and EV charging station incentive programs can send a clear, long-term policy signal to drive EV adoption and address key EV infrastructure challenges. However, few incentive programs to date have incorporated LCFS provisions into their design. Where LCFS policies exist, structural barriers can hinder site hosts' ability to generate benefits from participating in the LCFS. More thoughtful integration of LCFS and EV charging station incentive programs can be mutually beneficial for achieving the goals of both policies; LCFS revenues can increase the attractiveness of participating in EV charger incentive programs, and EV charger incentive programs can serve as a platform to increase participation in LCFS. In the case of the CALeVIP program in the San Diego region, estimated LCFS revenues could become a valuable source of new program funding as well as a tool to offset station operational costs for site hosts. Governments looking to spur the adoption of EVs and low carbon fuels should consider how they can design LCFS regulations and EV charging station incentive programs in a way that creates multiple benefits for site hosts, recognizes EVs' ability to integrate renewable generation, and builds public awareness of supportive EV policies. Future programs can leverage lessons learned from California's experience to encourage more cost-effective, efficient, and synergistic achievement of climate and transportation electrification goals.

References

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- [4] At the time this publication was written, the CIs for reformulated gasoline (CaRFG) and ultra low sulfur diesel (ULSD) were 99.44 gCO₂e/MJ and 100.45 gCO₂e/MJ, respectively. See endnote 2.
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- [6] *California's Low Carbon Fuel Standard*, <http://www.cadelivers.org/low-carbon-fuel-standard/>, accessed on 2020-02-24
- [7] The standard previously required a 10 percent CI reduction by 2020 from 2010 levels. <https://ww3.arb.ca.gov/regact/2018/lcfs18/fro.pdf>
- [8] LCFS credits can be calculated with the following equation: credits = (CI_{standard} – CI_{electricity}/Energy Economy Ratio)*Energy Density*Energy Economy Ratio*10⁻⁶). The Energy Economy Ratio (EER) is a coefficient that

approximates the efficiency of a fuel used by a vehicle relative to a reference fuel such as gasoline or diesel. The EER for electricity for light-duty EVs is 3.4.

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- [10] These programs may provide incentives through direct rebates, tax incentives, or grants.
- [11] Site hosts refer to entities that have EV charging stations deployed on their property or at their facility. Site hosts may own the charging equipment on their premises.
- [12] “Networked” charging equipment refers to charging stations that are connected to a back-end network operations center and capable of collecting station utilization data.
- [13] A 2019 evaluation report produced by the New York State Energy Research and Development Authority found that even with incentives provided by its Charge NY program, the business case for EV charging services remains challenging and there remains no universal approach to overcome costs needed to achieve profits at a given site. *Assessing the Business Case for Hosting Electric Vehicle Charging Stations in New York State*, <https://www.atlasevhub.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/19-31-Business-Case-for-Hosting-Charging-Stations-for-publication-3.pdf>, accessed on 2020-02-25
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